

Rotorcraft Flight Test Automation - The Saga Continues...

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Abstract—The cost associated with the next generation rotorcraft testing, training, and support, using current techniques, promises to escalate in a predicted hostile fiscal environment. Aircraft testing, and the associated training and support, place large demands on flight vehicles, avionics, weapons systems, test teams and scarce fiscal resources. Innovative technology options in the form of case based reasoning, automatic test plan and test report generation, intelligent documents, intelligent interfaces, and test plan rehearsal options can be used to assist flight test plan development, test reporting, and test data analysis. Integrating an enhanced generic structure, physics-based simulation model with the flight test automation software presents an option to run the test analytically while the test plan is being generated. The initial results include the capability to generate a comprehensive rotorcraft test plan, including related lesson learned, in approximately 15 minutes, on a personal computer at the test team work area. If the personal computer is tied into a workstation based comprehensive aircraft simulation program via a network, then selected tests from the test plan flight test matrix can be run analytically to give test team members a preview of what results to expect from the actual flight test. This flight test automation concept presents one option to enable rotorcraft flight testing to be done better, faster, cheaper, and safer. The work has been sponsored by a variety of low-key in-house, direct tasking, and small business initiatives and the rotorcraft flight test automation saga continues.

Introduction

Background—Factors such as declining budgets, reduced staffs, increased project cost, and tightened delivery schedules all point to the need to improve the current flight test process. The cost associated with the next generation rotorcraft testing, training, and support, using current techniques, promises to escalate in a predicted hostile fiscal environment. Vision 21 [1] calls for a

reduction in the current test and evaluation (T&E) infrastructure. The Simulation, Test and Evaluation Process (STEP) [2] and DoD Regulation 5000.2-R [3] require modeling and simulation throughout the system life cycle. Zittel [4] reviews the DoD Simulation Support Plan which calls for "... increasing emphasis on the use of modeling and simulation (M&S) in our acquisition programs to reduce cost and schedule without sacrificing quality or performance." Simulation based acquisition is considered an effective, affordable mechanism for fielding complex technologies and may help to make DoD a "smart buyer" [5]. Automated Test and Evaluation Master Plan (TEMP) programs and automated test plan programs have been ongoing for some time, as described below.

Related Work

ATPS—The Office of Secretary of Defense (OSD) sponsored an effort to use expert system based tools to automate the Test and Evaluation Master Plan (TEMP). This SAIC program [6] called Automated Test Planning System (ATPS) involved a joint approach to enhance and standardize TEMP development and review. ATPS includes DoD 5000.2-M chapters in hypertext, ACAT III Session Information Window, and Program Risk Assessment Module.

TEP—The Test and Evaluation Plan (TEP) Builder was developed by the Army Test and Evaluation Command, PRC Inc., and the University of Michigan to support Army operational test and evaluation (OT&E). The TEP Builder includes several different programs, including the knowledge base and tool set, that execute simultaneously on a workstation. The TEP was designed primarily for new testers with strong service-related expertise, but little familiarity with the OT&E process [7]

TEST_PLAN—The TEST_PLAN automated test planning software was initially demonstrated by G & C Systems in 1989 at a flight test symposium where it caught the attention of a Swedish aircraft manufacturer [8]. TEST_PLAN is a workstation-based software package that helps flight test engineers plan and track flight test programs by providing test points, maneuvers, test plans, planning constraints, and flight cards and reports options. The program uses relational data bases and expert systems, provides a computer graphics interface, and uses a built-in linear simulation model. Customized versions of TEST_PLAN have been developed for Saab Scania AB and NASA Dryden.

TEST PAWES—The Performance Assessment and Workload Evaluation System (PAWES) was developed by Arvin/Calspan and sponsored by the Air Force Armstrong Laboratory. It was developed to enhance crewstation evaluations during flight test [9]. PAWES is PC based and features process support, test planning, postflight data collection, data analysis and evaluation, and test report tools. The typical PAWES computer data display would include file information, strip chart data, digitized cockpit video, and animated aircraft drivers.

PROFTE—A Planning and Reporting Organizer For Test Engineers (PROFTE) was developed by McDonnell Douglas Corporation to support F/A-18E flight testing [10]. The requirements facing the F/A-18E program included a large number of test flights with the associated data points, seven aircraft, six test sites, a large diverse group of users and a very limited budget. PROFTE is a PC based system that uses the MicroSoft Access database and helps the test team members prepare test plan work descriptions, prepare flight cards, track test points, prepare flight reports, and report test program progress.

AFTES—This concept was initiated as a low-key, in-house Navy Patuxent River test plan development program in 1987 to use new software to support fixed-wing electro-optics testing. The program focus shifted to rotorcraft helicopter/ship and flying qualities and performance testing in FY89, and the concept was called the Test Plan Automation System (TPAS). Different expert shell structures were evaluated and limited work was performed to input flight test knowledge base information into the TPAS system. Funding for this initial work ended in 1992, and in 1994 two small business innovative research (SBIR) programs were initiated that renewed the effort. Stottler, Hienke, and Associates, Inc. (SHAI), was prime on the first SBIR and it focused on using artificial intelligence technology to enhance rotorcraft test planning, test reporting, data analysis, and project management. This SBIR program

project was called the Automated Flight Test Engineering System (AFTES), and the concept is illustrated in figure 1. Advanced Rotorcraft Technology (ART) was prime on the second SBIR program and it focused on developing a PC tutorial to support rotorcraft handling qualities, flight control system, and loads testing, as shown in figure 2. The PC tutorial was also tied into a physics-based simulation model which permits interactive design and test options. The SBIR efforts have been supplemented by limited direct task sponsors, and in 1996 by a limited high performance computer (HPC) program on flight test automation using HPC. Thus, the saga on rotorcraft flight test automation continues, and this paper reviews the overall effort and presents examples of flight test applications.

Purpose—Flight test automation options focusing on simulation may play a role in reducing the cost and time required to test the next generation aircraft and related systems. A goal of this concept includes developing the capability to run a comprehensive analytical flight test program for a rotorcraft in one day that currently might take more than a year of actual testing. A second goal includes enhancing real-time simulation to better support flight testing. The current generation of operational flight trainers and/or engineering simulators are usually vehicle specific, with no integrated capability to support test plan development and report generation. The current operational flight trainers are also very expensive and are very limited in their ability to support flight testing. Flight trainers are especially limited in their ability to predict loads and in their ability to support at-sea flight test scenarios. If aircraft flight limits, specification limits, and component loads limits were built into the simulation model, this information could be presented on the data plots, to show test team members and others how close the planned flight would approach a limit. This paper discusses how integrating and enhancing flight test automation software and a physics-based simulation model could be used to support and help automate rotorcraft flight testing.

Flight Test Requirements—Aircraft requirements range from concept to disposal over the life cycle of the vehicle. Decisions made early in the acquisition cycle can have a big influence on flight test requirements. Test and evaluation may focus on developmental testing or operational testing. Developmental testing has characteristically focused on aircraft test management, test planning, instrumentation, flight testing, data analysis, and test reporting. This classical testing is expensive, dependent on atmospheric conditions, requires access to a large test support system, and aircraft changes made at this stage can be very costly to the program budget and schedule. Past flight testing has developed a

very large test knowledge base, which is often lost when key personnel change jobs or test organizations are closed as a result of downsizing or mergers. Electronic options are available to store the large flight test database, and the concept of a “paperless” flight test program is gaining more momentum.

Flight Test Automation Requirements—Flight test automation refers to doing the testing first analytically, and it also implies pulling together all available technologies, knowledge, and lessons learned to optimize the process. Two basic components are required to make this happen: 1) automation software that focuses on test planning, test reporting, data analysis, and project management, and 2) a physics-based simulation model that has a generic structure that can be readily set-up to represent a variety of aircraft and/or related systems at selected levels of fidelity. If possible, these two components should be connected with a seamless interface. Rotorcraft flight test automation requirements are summarized in figure 3.

Test Automation—One of the key elements of a successful flight test program is a comprehensive flight test plan. Flight test automation options often start with test planning. The test plan format is established by the test activity and the content of the test plan is a function of the type of test to be conducted. A sample flight test plan format contains the standard background, purpose, test equipment, test methods, and administrative sections, plus emphasis on safety considerations, including checklists, potential hazards, and test flight and/or loading restrictions. Test plans must be generated for a variety of air vehicle tests, as illustrated in table 1. Note that a test plan may be written for more than one type of test (i.e., flying qualities and performance or FQ&P). Other test types like helicopter/ship or Dynamic Interface (DI) testing involve both aircraft and ship. It is estimated that there are over 35 ship classes that support helicopter operations and thus require testing to determine operational flight envelopes. DI testing involves determining the operational capability of a particular type rotorcraft operating on a particular class ship. One important aspect of rotorcraft flight test automation is the need to consolidate a very large test knowledge base and present it to the test team members.

Table 1
Typical Navy & Marine Corps Rotorcraft
(Army & Air Force Rotorcraft Not Shown)

AH-1W	SH-2G	UH-3H	MV-22	CH-46E	CH-53D	TH-57C	SH-60B	UAV's
UH-1N		VH-3D		UH-46D	RH-53D		SH-60F	
					CH-53E		HH-60H	
					MH-53E			

Simulation—It is hard to imagine all the possible applications of simulation, and, as noted earlier, simulation is now required on all major DOD acquisition programs. It is amazing what simulation can do to support flight testing, but it is even more amazing what simulation cannot do to support flight testing, especially rotorcraft flight testing. Real time operational flight trainers have been used for years, but these trainer models usually have simplified rotor models, point source fuselage models, and are vehicle specific. Flight testing can be done on a variety of aircraft models, and the test team members may request information on what happens if a number of parameters are varied through specified ranges, including information on rotor, fuselage, and external loads, on downwash, and information on how close a planned flight maneuver might approach an aircraft limit.

Air Vehicle Simulation—If there was only one vehicle to simulate, which some people have theorized may be the

case in about 2050 [5], the simulation challenge would be relatively small, and there would be no requirement for a standard or generic simulation structure. A Navy flight test activity may work with a wide variety of fixed-wing aircraft, rotorcraft, and UAV's, plus related systems. If the activity had the world's best AH-1W model, it could not be used to support H-46 testing, training, or mission rehearsal. If the activity had a good H-46 model, it could not be used to support H-60 test programs. In this case, having a generic model structure, with a standard model input data format can be used to facilitate model set-up. The model may be implemented as a rotormap model or blade element model. The blade element model may have either rigid or elastic blades. The rotorcraft in table 1 have a variety of rotor hub types, including teetering (2 bladed) and articulated (3+ blades, and flap, lead-lag, and feathering hinges) configurations. The rotorcraft model may have a variety of inflow models and blade airloads models. The ability to select the level of model complexity or fidelity required for the specific task is important.

Current Status

The rotorcraft flight test automation work to date has focused primarily on enhancing and enlarging the flight test knowledge base, enhancing the generic simulation structure's flight test interface, and developing an interface between the two programs. Much of the work on the AFTES has focused on acquiring sample rotorcraft flight test plans for the program knowledge base, and developing the ability to rapidly generate a comprehensive test plan. The initial program focus has been on developing a template to support helicopter/ship or DI test planning. Once AFTES is selected, the team member is asked to give his/her name and select a test group. Current selectable groups are listed below:

- Avionics Testing (AV)
- Dynamic Interface Testing (DI)
- Engine Testing
- Flight Control System Testing (FCS)
- Flying Qualities & Performance (FQ&P)
- Reliability & Maintainability (R&M)
- Simulator Data Acquisition
- Structural Test
- Operations (OPS) (Test plan status info)

After the team member name and group name data have been entered, the main AFTES window appears. The main window functions are outlined below:

- Test Planning
 - Test Plan Development
 - Similar Test Plan Retrieval
 - Test Point Retrieval
- Test Reporting
 - Test Report Development
 - Similar Test Point Retrieval
- Data Analysis
 - Calibrations
 - Pilot Cards
 - Data Format
 - Data Reduction
 - Data Presentation
- Project Management
 - Current Project Status
 - Related Projects

Selecting Test Plan Development brings up a data input sheet which asks for the following types of information for a DI test plan:

- Pilots
- Engineers
- Test Aircraft
- Test Ships
- Date of Test
- Brief Date
- Date of Pre-Sail Conference
- Special Equipment
- Type of Test
- Other Equipment
- Project Cost Calculation
- Edit Cover Sheet
- Edit Appendices
- Show Related Lessons Learned
- Define Output File
- Generate Test Plan

For DI test plan generation, selecting type of test gives the following options:

- Launch/Recovery Envelope Development
- Aviation Facilities Compatibility Evaluation
- Lighting Evaluation for NVG and Non-NVD Operations
- SSGTG Exhaust Gases Compatibility Evaluation
- Ordnance/Deck Clearance Evaluation
- NVD HUD Evaluation
- Expanding Gross Weight Performance Evaluation
- Fixed Stabilator Flying Qualities Evaluation
- VERTREP Suitability Evaluation
- Rotor Engage/Disengage Evaluation

All the above type tests are selectable, except for rotor engage/disengage testing which has not been implemented. If the first nine DI type tests listed above are selected, and the input field data inserted, and the generate test plan option selected, AFTES will take about 15 minutes on a Pentium PC to generate a comprehensive test plan of about 90 pages, including checklists and lessons learned. Future versions of AFTES will include an online option to the US Naval Test Pilot School manual for helicopter test procedures and data analysis examples.

For the basic FQ&P type air vehicle tests, one test plan appendix presents a summary of planned flights and the test conditions for each flight. This appendix is called the flight test matrix and each flight is represented as one row in the

matrix as shown in table 2. The flight test matrix is generated by AFTES, and it is important to be able to analytically fly all the planned test flights listed in the matrix while developing the test plan.

Simulation Structure—A physics-based simulation model is a key element in the rotorcraft flight test automation process. One example of a generic structure, physics-based simulation model is the Advanced Rotorcraft Technology's FLIGHTLAB program. Although the basic FLIGHTLAB simulation code has been available for some time, an X-Windows version (Xanalysis) was released in 1997. The Xanalysis program includes options to load any model set-up in the FLIGHTLAB structure, a variety of analysis options, applications, and a real-time pilot-in-the-loop run option. Applications include analytical support for flight testing, rotor

loads/downwash testing, airframe loads testing, and handling qualities testing. The flight test support option uses a flight test matrix format, which is the same format used in the test plan flight test matrix. The current list of tests in the Xanalysis test matrix include:

- Hover
- Critical Azimuth
- Low Speed
- Level Flight
- Forward Climb
- Longitudinal Static Stability
- Static Lateral Stability
- Longitudinal Dynamic Stability
- Coordinated Turn
- Autorotation

Table 2
Typical Flight Test Matrix

Test No.	Test Type	Test Conditions				Test Configurations			FCS Status	Pilot Options	Remarks
		A/S KCAS	Hp FT	OAT °C	NR RPM	WT LB	CG INFRL	Loading			
1	Hover										
2	Vertical Climbs										
3	Critical Azimuth										
4	Static Stability										
etc.	etc.										

Test conditions (i.e., airspeed, altitude, temperature, and rotor speed), test configurations (i.e., weight and center of gravity), flight control system status, and plot formats for results can be entered in the test matrix for each test. Tests can be selected and run individually or as a group from the flight test matrix. All ten tests in the flight test matrix can be run overnight on a single 150 Mz processor workstation. The Xanalysis program also has a parameter sweep test support option. This means that the test team member could rapidly set up the program to vary a large number of parameters to determine the effect for certain flight conditions. One example includes a six parameter sweep of selected test parameters associated with a low airspeed test of a specified aircraft model. The sweep parameters are presented below, and the analysis required more than 30,000 simulation model trim points.

Sweep Parameters

- Longitudinal center of gravity
- Lateral center of gravity
- Pressure altitude

- Air temperature
- Wind speed
- Wind direction

Although the parameter sweep is very easy to set up, this problem requires more than 3 weeks of CPU time running on a single 150 Mz processor workstation. If the program could distribute the calculations over a series of processors or if the problem was broken down into smaller parameter sweep groups, the calculations would be much faster.

The Xanalysis simulation structure can also be used to generate analytical predictions for the simulated model rotor blade, rotor hub, and pitch link forces and moments to support structures and loads testing. A handling quality analysis option can be used to determine the simulated model damping, quickness, bandwidth, and other flying qualities requirements specified in aeronautical design standard ADS-33 [11]. Work is currently ongoing to

develop a PC tutorial to support rotorcraft handling qualities, flight controls, and loads testing.

Considerable progress has been made on the concept of rotorcraft flight test automation. The AFTES can be used to generate a comprehensive helicopter/ship test plan, including lessons learned, in about 15 minutes. Selected air vehicle tests can be run from the AFTES test plan flight test matrix using an interface to the Xanalysis simulation program. This work has the potential to help permit future rotorcraft flight testing to be done better, faster, cheaper, and safer. It is very difficult to get support for this type of work, but the rotorcraft flight test automation saga continues.

Future Recommendations

Ongoing work—Work is ongoing to enhance both the flight test automation software and the generic simulation structure. This work includes extending the AFTES testing planning to cover other rotorcraft types of flight testing in addition to helicopter/ship or Dynamic Interface testing. Work is also planned to enhance the report, data analysis, and management sections of AFTES, plus adding voice recognition technology. A larger test plan, test report, and lessons learned multi-service database is needed.

Work is ongoing to develop a PC tutorial on handling qualities, flight controls, and loads testing that is integrated with the Xanalysis generic simulation program. Work is also ongoing to better define the effects of helicopter off-axis coupling, engine modeling, and improved loads prediction capability.

Future recommendations—Enhancements are needed to help optimize both AFTES and Xanalysis to support flight testing. The generic structure simulation program, Xanalysis, needs to be setup for a variety of rotorcraft and PC tutorials need to be developed for all types of rotorcraft testing. The model's ability to predict loads, interactive aerodynamics, engine dynamics, and edge of flight envelope maneuver limits needs to be improved. Flight test limits need to be built into the program, and a built-in simulation model validation option is also needed.

A robust design simulation, as shown in figure 4, and advanced 3-D visual modeling and testing could be added to the physics-based simulation model and the flight test automation software to provide a virtual design and test capability at the test team work area.

Validation Options—Validation is important for flight test automation software and simulation models. Validation is often discussed in terms of verification, validation and accreditation (VV&A), where standard definitions apply. New test plans and reports can be compared to existing test plans and reports for the same rotorcraft and type of test. The simulation model response to classical air vehicle maneuvers can be compared to actual flight test data. If validation options could be built into the simulation model, validation could be readily demonstrated to potential users. Future validation options should also consider the 3-D rotorcraft flight environment, as well as, all air vehicle flight limits. Parameter sweep techniques should also be incorporated into future validation programs to help confirm model acceptability throughout the aircraft flight envelope.

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Biography

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Figure 1
Automated Flight Test Engineering System

Figure 2
Personal Computer Tutorial on Handling Qualities, Controls, and Loads

Figure 3
Rotorcraft Flight Test Automation Overview

Figure 4
Affordable Advanced Virtual Integrated Test and Training Applications Proposal